

Relationships between galaxies, halos and large-scale structure

Houjun Mo
(Tsinghua/UMass)

Link galaxies to dark matter halos

Methods

Halo occupation distribution (HOD);
Conditional luminosity function (CLF);
Abundance matching;
Empirical model;
Semi-analytic model (SAM);
Numerical simulations.

Based on galaxy groups

Selecting galaxy groups to represent dark matter halos

The halo-based group finder
of Yang et al. (2005):

$M \rightarrow (r, \sigma)$

Lim et al test with EAGLE

M^* (halo mass proxy)

Conditional luminosity/stellar mass functions

$$\Phi(L|M)$$

Faint-end upturn

SDSS Groups

For red galaxies: $M_* \propto M_{\text{ph}}$;
 For blue galaxies $M_* \propto M_{\text{ph}}^{3/2}$

at low-mass end

Halo-galaxy connection: An empirical approach

Empirical model adopted needs to be general but simple to avoid over-fitting

$$\dot{M}_\star = \mathcal{E} \frac{f_b M_{\text{vir}}}{\tau_0} (1+z)^\eta (X+1)^\alpha \left(\frac{X+\mathcal{R}}{X+1} \right)^\beta \left(\frac{X+\mathcal{R}}{X} \right)^\gamma$$

where \mathcal{E} overall efficiency; f_b cosmic baryon mass fraction; τ_0 is the dynamic timescale at present day, and $\eta = \eta' + 3/2$.

$$X \equiv M_{\text{vir}}/M_c; \quad \mathcal{R} < 1.$$

Two characteristic masses: M_c and $\mathcal{R}M_c$, and three slopes: α , β and γ . All of them may depend on z .

Halo merger trees and galaxy stripping and merger treated as in semi-analytic model.

Also needs advanced sampling methods (e.g. MCMC, MULTINEST) to explore parameter space

Model inferences from observed CLFs

Consistent with the inferences from
the observed galaxy LFs/SMFs at different redshifts

Model Predictions

Galaxy mass-halo mass relation:

Star formation histories of central galaxies in present halos of different masses:

Model-III

$$z_c = 2.2 \pm 0.5$$

matches upturn

Model-II

does not match

Model Predictions

Solid line: star formation; dashed: assembly

Mass acquisition: dominated by SF except in mass halos

Prediction of SMFs at high z

SFRD

Data: Hopkins & Beacom 2006;
Bouwens et al. 2012

Massive Submm
galaxies are
sub-dominant at
any time

Galaxies and LSS

Δ : Large-scale environmental parameter, such as galaxy number density, mass density, tidal field, etc.

$$P(G|\Delta) = \int P(G|H, \Delta)P(H|\Delta)dH$$

$$P'(G|\Delta) \equiv \int P(G|H, \Delta)P(H)dH$$

$P' = P$ if $P(G|H, \Delta)$ is independent of H

Similarly:

$$P(G|H) = \int P(G|H, \Delta)P(\Delta|H)d\Delta$$

$$P'(G|H) \equiv \int P(G|H, \Delta)P(\Delta)d\Delta$$

$P' = P$ if $P(G|H, \Delta)$ is independent of Δ

Density field from reconstruction

Wang et al. 2014; 2016

The Great Wall Region

Mass densities vs. Galaxy densities

Δ : Local mass density (reconstructed) smoothed on $5\text{Mpc}/h$ radius;
 Δ_g : Local mass density calculated using 5 nearest neighbors.

Quenching of galaxies in different environments

Halo mass dependence: similar for centrals and satellites

Model A: local density is the cause; halo-mass dependence only through halo bias

Model B:

halo mass is the cause;
density dependence
only through halo bias.

centrals and galaxies
treated the same way

Difference between
observation and model

Model C:
Model B combined
with assembly bias

**Difference between
observation and
model**

Quenching efficiency is **independent** of galaxy mass in halos of given mass

$$\varepsilon(m, E|E_0) \equiv \frac{F_q(m, E) - F_q(m, E_0)}{1 - F_q(m, E_0)}$$

Also Peng et al.; Woo et al.

But the zero-point (set by self-quenching) depends strongly on galaxy mass

$$F_q(m|\Delta_0) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{m}{m'}\right)^d\right] \quad m' \approx 5 \times 10^{10} h^{-2} M_\odot; \quad d \approx 0.75$$

Summary

- The galaxy-halo connection provides a powerful way to summarize observational data and to make predictions under the assumption of a given cosmology.
- Halo mass and assembly bias are the main driving forces of the environmental dependence of quenching of star formation in galaxies, with efficiency independent of galaxy mass.
- Strong galaxy-mass dependence in self quenching to set zero point for environmental quenching.